

Spiritual Intelligence in Supply Chain Management

Pallikkara Viswanthan

Member Indian Institute of Materials Management, Bangalore

Abstract:

In supply chain the capacity of an individual to possess a social understanding, of all relevant purpose in life, also to understand self, have a high degree of conscience, compassion, in order to have a human value in supply chain. Supply chain enjoys spiritual intelligence also the increased ability to pick out the actions required, experience, beliefs, values, that is liable to create greater harmony, for the purpose to have in our individual lives, a superiority in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence in many of the supply chain organisation, have lost what is constituted as soul, as the souls work to nurture supply chain, as also, it becomes necessary to attach the souls, with the chance to be capable, of being employed on doing the necessary work in supply chain, with the term constituted as spiritual intelligence in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence leadership in supply chain holds the attitude towards values, considered as important, to intrinsically motivate the aspects in supply chain, also have the initiative to connect to others feelings in supply chain, also to the outer world, as this incorporates the sense of meanings, well-beings, vision, culture of people, the likeliness, also the feeling of being appreciated in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence in supply chain, considered as a personal security, affecting personal effectiveness, relationship building, inter-personal relationship, managing change, building inter-personal relationship, removing obstacles' in supply chain, with practical implication, with special interest to human resource management, giving organisation value in supply chain, using spiritual intelligence as a logic of analysis to make, discuss emotional intelligence, that is needed to understand, control emotions, feeling to the sensitiveness, of the supply chain.

Key Words: Spiritual intelligence leadership, resource management, relationship building, control emotions.

Introduction:

Supply chain spiritual intelligence has created to become a success in any organization, which is also considered as an expression of spiritual qualities in supply chain, through

attitudes, thoughts, of the supply chain, which are engaged in working in place of supply chain, helping to enlighten, guide future places of work, reforms, better policies, also bring a positive results in supply chain.

Supply chain has become extremely competitive, in order to keep pace with the globalization, trying to meet the requirements, it is observed that supply chain has to be ahead of the competitive benchmark. Spiritual intelligence orientation in supply chain engages manpower, in various activities, which have meaningful aspect in relation to both natures, the essence of being with the society in supply chain. Spiritual intelligence, as unit of measure allows manpower to look at problems, related to the meaning of value, in supply chain, so that it can be placed at the appropriate level with richer meaning, of value in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence in supply chain deals with realisation of the mental aptitude, that contributes to spiritual intelligence of the workmen, their performance in the organisation, however it has been confirmed that spiritual intelligence in supply chain, has been affecting the human behaviour, however, as that it had become necessary to analyse the co-relationship between spiritual relationship, also that of the manpower established in supply chain.

Purpose of The Study:

Supply chain can also have an higher level of spiritual intelligence, the manpower requirement can have inspirational motivation, for devotion, work, better outcome, better production, improve organisation performance, with a considerate and a good level of spiritual intelligence that be adorned as an asset in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence is considered of the higher dimension of supply chain, with qualities, capabilities, with authentic, in the form of wisdom, integrity, joy, love, creativity, peace, that have to be necessarily utilized in supply chain. Spiritual intelligence results in a sense of deeper attachment towards spiritual attachment for a purpose in supply chain, especially during the period of epidemic, combined with vast improvement, in wide range of important skills, work skills in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence in supply chain is also to realise that it is to bring awareness in the organisation, thus expand the capacity, to understand the behaviour of the customer, also the consumers' requirement in supply chain. Spiritual intelligence allows discerning the true

cause of behaviour, without any judgement, serving the needs during the epidemic, until supply chain is to meet the demand, also the needs that meet the requirement in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence performances through understanding in supply chain support the innate strengths of the manpower, as spiritual intelligence is able to drive performance through the empathy, awareness or requirement of the manpower. Spiritual intelligence is able to drive the performance the latent's, which manifests through nurturing, monitoring, in supply chain.

Literature Review:

Spiritual influence are sometimes considered as a boon to supply chain, since it considers the best activity, is to get out of the inherent activities, that are considered to be very turbulent, at the times of needed, when the observation of profit is not alone a given preference in pursuit of happiness, or profit that necessarily contributing 75% in supply chain

Spiritual intelligence in supply chain helps to instil human value, organisational culture, within the supply chain. Spiritual intelligence is the ability to think act with a wise wisdom, good compassion, maintaining inner outer power, peace, respective of the situation arising about 60% in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence is the ability to create a meaning based on deep understanding, of essential requirements, awareness of the ability by using multiple levels of consciousness in problem solving, interconnecting all the transactions among 75% of the supply chain.

The ability to include in Spiritual intelligence is the concept of true behaviour, in order to improve the sustainability, risk, stress effectiveness, dealing with health behaviour, mental disorder in an organized manpower with substantial development 50% in supply chain.

Research Methodology:

Spiritual intelligence research is to focus on global social environment, economic conditions, sustainability, challenges, which may sometimes lack values in supply chain, but they are not to be disconnected from the values that are stated in human behaviour, in which manpower lack motivation, in a deep seated spiritual intelligence malaise in supply chain, putting the matter over right for the validity purpose with a way of moving forward, within the way in spiritual intelligence in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence has researched that in supply chain, which has the self-efficacy, (persons belief in the ability to succeed in particular situation) in health behaviour, significantly being correlated, as self efficacy showed partial mediation between spiritual intelligence in health behaviour in supply chain. Spiritual intelligence can boost positive health behaviour, as it is associated with self-efficacy in health behaviour in supply chain

Spiritual intelligence has been into research, as the capacity of supply chain, can transcend to the physical activity of the material content, the ability to experience the heightened state of consciousness, with the ability to satisfy the everyday experience in supply chain, so also to

utilize the spiritual resources available in supply chain, in order to solve the problems of capacity building in the most virtuous way in supply chain.

Results:

Spiritual intelligence is always considered to be of a broader of higher dimension of intelligences, which necessarily activates the qualities, capabilities, of an authentic state of affairs in the form of wisdom, compassion, integrity, joy, love, creativity, peace to the manpower development in supply chain.

A set of mental capabilities that contribute to the capacity of Spiritual intelligence, the awareness, also the integration with an adaptive application of the non-material content, of being transcendent, in supply chain, with the aspects of the ones that are in existence leading to such of the outcome, with deep existential reflection (exploring the problems of human existence) enhancement of recognition of self transcendent of mastering of spiritual intelligence in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence is the ability with the meaning of various issues of supply chain life activities, concerning manpower, health activities, life, behaviours in supply chain, with a meaningful context adhered in supply chain, is also a believer of highest contact of spiritual intelligence, with the capacity of spiritual intelligence to improve dealing with sustainability, risk, disruption, epidemic, unforeseen conditions, in order to improve efficiently the well being of the stress, calamity in supply chain.

Discussions and Findings:

Spiritual intelligence transactional communication in the organisation, explores the communication between the leader of the organisation in supply chain, also with new employees, in which the leader is able to recognize the means of obtaining the needs of motivation, discipline, trust, from the employee, by establishing good relation, with better communication, approach to establish a new emergent with the context that communication will be shared, as an emerging reality, with proper human behaviour, towards an objective, situation, so as to be established in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence is the ability to access higher values meaningfully, by dividing the purposes, of unconscious aspects of the supply chain, which is to be embedded, with the meaning, values, and purposes of having a creative supply chain. Spiritual intelligence include the ability to think away from supply chain aspects, humility, also access to energy, that just come beyond the supply chain activities, on a day to day concern in supply chain.

Supply chain spiritual intelligence allows creative thinking, outside the supply chain activities, ability to change ideas, also to alter the situations as and when necessary, allow to deal with greatness in supply chain, giving the capacity for a paradox to choose the right thing in supply chain, whether the right is considered for a situation in supply chain. Spiritual intelligence enables supply chain, to think about the decisions, of what is best to be considered in supply chain, than as a single entity in supply chain, bringing awareness beyond the consideration in supply chain, thus create an impact on supply chain.

Future Work/Conclusions/Recommendations:

Spiritual intelligence in supply chain is considered for a flexible capacity, with high degree of self-awareness, also the capacity to adhere to the consequences, quality, inspired by vision, values, also the reluctance to cause any harm in supply chain.

Spiritual intelligence enhances the capacity in supply chain, qualities, compassion, creativity, wisdom, improving the awareness in the supply chain, feeling connected with the outside world in supply chain. Spiritual intelligence can be considered as an important individual, varying in ways of handling ethical dilemmas, observing the existence in supply chain.

Work place in spiritual intelligence has a deep sense of meaning, promoting greater motivation, organizing prosperity, as it is researched in spiritual intelligence helps to improve the occupational commitment of supply chain, helps to the capacity to tolerate, adapt, with occupations, understand, stay calm, focus on the intricate portion in supply chain, promoting better occupational strength or commitment in overall development of the organisation in supply chain.

References:

1. **The Role of Spiritual Intelligence in Business**, Richard (Rick), Mcknight Phd.
2. **Effective of Spiritual Intelligence on Effective Change Management**, A review of Selected Research, Muneeba Ali Ali Hasan, Electronic Research Journal.
3. **Practical Application of Spiritual Intelligence Work Place**, Mike George, Gavius Media:
4. **Emotional and Spiritual Intelligence For Managerial Effectiveness & Conquering Stress**, Mdi Campus Gurgeon.